

30TH INTERNATIONAL MONTESSORI CONGRESS

DIGITAL PROGRAM

View our
online catalog

20%
disco unt*
code: **IMC26**

Learning
is in the details

* This offer is valid for 20% off for all participants of the IMC Congress, applies to all products through May 10th, 2026, and cannot be combined with any other specials, discounts, and/or offers.

nienhuis[®]
montessori since 1929

MAY 1ST

(09:30 - 22:00)

15:00-16:00

OPENING CEREMONY
MONTESSORI MÉXICO / AMI
CIC ROOMS 3-4

16:00-16:45

THE HOPE AND THE PROMISE
BLUE BLOCKS MONTESSORI (INDIA)
MONTESSORI ADOLESCENTS
CIC ROOMS 3-4

16:00-17:30

COFFEE BREAK
CIC EXHIBITOR'S AREA

17:30-18:50

OPENING KEYNOTE
BIOLOGY OF LOSS

DR. GABOR MATÉ CIC ROOMS 3-4

18:50-19:00

CLOSING REMARKS

19:30-22:00

WELCOME COCKTAIL
(REGISTERED PARTICIPANTS ONLY)

THE PINAR

THE PREPARED ENVIRONMENT

EXTENDS BEYOND THE CLASSROOM

Montessori Sports partners with schools redesigning movement, sports and PE environments with intention, purpose, and respect for the developing individual.

COME FIND US IN THE EXHIBITION HALL

**Montessori
Sports**

**WHERE SPORTS AND
MONTESSORI MEET**

the montessori experience:

Refresh Courses and More!

February 12-14, 2027
Orlando, Florida

Registration opens May 11

themontessorixperience.org

**AMI
USA**

**ASSOCIATION
MONTESSORI
INTERNATIONAL**

NEW!

AMI COURSES IN ST. LOUIS

Primary 3-6 Blended
Diploma Course
Begins July 2026

Primary 3-6 In-Person
Diploma Course
Begins September 2026

0-6 Online
Orientation Course
Begins September 2026

**MONTESSORI
TRAINING
CENTER** OF ST. LOUIS

MTCSTL.ORG

As the first and oldest AMI Training Center in the United States, WMI has trained nearly 3,000 teachers who have gone on to establish public, private, and charter schools in the Washington, DC area and beyond.

Est.
1962

Expanding Access Preparing Educators Supporting Community

Teacher Training

0-3, 3-6, 6-12

New 3-6 Course in Spanish

Professional Development
Mentorship

Early Childhood Programs

Cornerstone Montessori School

Birth to Five Montessori Family Program

Montessori Partners Serving All Children

Community-led Culturally-Responsive Programs

AMI EsF Recognized Initiative

Learn More: montessoricentermn.org

Montessori Science of Reading

